

Students' perception of teacher's strategies in teaching reading

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- Abstract : This research is motivated by the importance of students' English reading skills. However, not all students have the ability to read English well. In terms of perception, students can have individual feelings and opinions. Students should have their perception of which strategy is more effective and interesting that teachers use for reading skills. In reading learning, students prefer to use interesting and interactive strategies. This research was conducted to find out how students perceive the strategy used by teachers. The sample of this research was a tenth grader of 22 students at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang. The design of the research is qualitative descriptive and uses the instruments of questionnaires and interviews. The results of the research are described in the form of pie charts and descriptions. The research concluded that the strategies used by teachers can help students develop their reading skills. Besides, students also agreed and liked the strategy used which made most students feel interested, comfortable, and more active in following reading learning. Overall it was found that many of them expressed a positive response to the strategies used by teachers in learning
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1. Introduction

English is a global language used for global interaction, taught in Indonesia from kindergarten to university (Astuti, 2013:1). Therefore, English is extensively studied by students in Indonesia and around the world. English is one of Indonesia's most popular higher education majors. English as a Foreign Language in Indonesia (Mazidah, 2023:139). In teaching and learning English, four abilities must be known. They are listening, speaking, reading, and writing. According to (Harmer, 2007:99) Reading is crucial for students' language acquisition and knowledge growth, requiring practice and understanding to connect ideas and gain meaning from text. Reading is an activity that seeks to find various pieces of information contained in reading in the form of understanding (Masruroh, 2022:89). Reading abilities are vital in the lives of good students both now and in the future. Furthermore, (Harmer, 2001:283) defines reading as a receptive skill, involving the extraction of meaning from language through the eyes and brain, a mechanism that involves the processing of visual information.

Reading activity is a strategy that gives instructional support to help students before, during, and after reading. (Betts, 2012:67-86). The teacher plays an important role in preparing children for reading by teaching vocabulary, eliciting prior knowledge, teaching specific reading skills, and setting a reading goal. Reading activities include pre-reading, during-reading, and post-reading. Pre-reading tasks include predicting words, sequencing pictures, and sharing information. During-reading activities include modeling reading, skimming, rereading, and summarizing the book. After-reading activities include tale creation and reader discussion (Gibbons and Cummins, 2002: 165). In learning reading there are many difficulties that students have among others, the lack of vocabulary that they have so they have difficulty in dealing with a text and too long reading text so they are easily bored in learning.

Regarding this fact, Teachers should be aware of their significant role in the development of pupils' reading skills. Teachers have a responsibility to help children improve their reading skills. According to the author's experience performing a study at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang, teachers used a range of tactics for reading learning. According to Setiyadi (2006:55), Teachers can use a variety of strategies to teach reading, such as authentic material, classroom reading aloud, comprehension questions, text difficulty level checks, pre-reading activities, vocabulary development, understanding the text's heart, contextual clues, teaching reading strategies, visualizing written content, providing multiple reading purposes, and identifying texts and tasks. In learning reading many strategies that teachers can use, the teacher prefers to use strategies to analyze vocabulary, previewing, Summarizing, and QARs because they are easier to understand. Thus, the use of such a strategy leads students' enthusiasm and active learning reading to be increased. The several strategies, some of them can be applied in teaching reading of several text types taught in Indonesia. Analytical exposition is one of the material given to tenth-grade students. Analytical exposition text is a sort of spoken or written text meant to persuade listeners or readers of anything in this context (Yue Sri, 2019:1).

Perception is a process of being aware of or understanding sensory information. Furthermore, it claimed that sensing entails obtaining stimuli through sensory devices. It continues, leading to perception, in which people have different opinions regarding information Walgito (2010:99). Perception is a person's brain's opinion, with positive thinking resulting in a positive perception, and students' perceptions are their point of view towards learning processes and suggestions for improvement by teachers or classmates (Shidu, 2003:15). three main characteristics affect our perception of other people. There are three aspects related to perception that influence how we perceive the object of perception (Ningsih & Fata, 2015). There are familiarity, Familiarity, mood, and self-concept are key factors in perception, with familiarity influencing objects, mood influencing perception, and self-concept determining the perceiver's perception. Two factors of influence impact perception: external and internal

factors. Internal factors perception from the individual, such as interest, attention, and physiological (Ismail & Fata, 2016). The characteristics of the surroundings and the topic matter are considered external elements. It alters one's perspective on the environment and on how other people feel or accept them. From the previous description, students' perception encompasses their opinions, beliefs, and hopes for positive future events, as well as their demand for accurate and genuine information.

The research is conducted based on previous research. The first is Loebis's (2014) Students' perception of teacher strategies to motivate the students in extensive reading classes. The researcher used a strategy to motivate students in extensive reading classes and the data of this study was collected using a semi-structured interview. By analyzing it qualitatively, the finding revealed that students perceived that the teacher's support is important in their learning process.

The second, Pasaribu, (2020) Students' perception on E-learning toward reading comprehension in SMP IT Bunayya Pekanbaru. This research was used qualitatively by using questionnaires and interviews. The result showed that from the questionnaire, the majority of students were enough. It means that students' perspective about e-learning on reading comprehension at SMP IT Bunayya was enough good. Based on the interview session all students agree that e-learning helps a lot while learning English.

The third, Purnomo, (2021) Students' perception in Online Learning Towards Reading Comprehension at the Tenth Graders of SMA Negeri 1 Kota Jambi. Based on the results of pre-research at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Jambi, the researcher found that the students were lack of understanding in reading. Comprehending the text is the problem students meet in reading. The students said that comprehending a reading text was a difficult task to do especially when it came in the form of an examination or test. This condition is also affected by the use of online learning activities.

Based on the description above, the researcher will conduct research entitled "Students' perception towards teacher's Strategies in teaching reading for the Tenth Graders at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang". The researchers chose the title because there are phenomena or problems in this research. Such as students' low interest in reading and the lack of vocabulary they know. So, this research needs to be done to confirm, answer, or know the existing problems.

2. Methods

In this research, the researcher used a descriptive qualitative. Qualitative research is a kind of research investigating and understanding the meaning individually or in groups related to social or human problems (Creswell, 2014:32). The subject of the research is the tenth graders at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang. This research used two instruments: a questionnaire and an interview. The questionnaire used close-ended and consisted of 25 statements. The researchers also applied structured interviews to interview students. The interviews are a supporting instrument that aims to find out how students perceive the strategies used by teachers. The interview consists of 15 questions that have been adapted and addressed to 22 students of the tenth grade at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang.

According to Miles and Huberman as cited in Sugiyono (2019:321), data analysis in qualitative research is carried out at the time of data collection and after completion of data collection at a certain period. The researcher will analyze data from questionnaires and interviews to find out the students' perception of teacher's strategies in teaching. Then, Data from the questionnaire will be analyzed, summarized, organized, and selected by substantive or focusing on important things. Data will be displayed in the form of pie charts and descriptions to make it easy to understand. Interview, the initial data in the interview is audio,

and then the researcher will transcribe the audio into text using the "speech to text" application. The data from interviews will be analyzed and described in sentences.

3. Finding and Discussion

Questionnaire

This stage displays the outcomes of the questionnaire about students' perception of teacher's strategies in teaching reading. Those were collected through a questionnaire distributed to 22 respondents who were chosen as a sample in this research. The questionnaire was distributed on 31 January and 7 February 2024 by using paper. There were 25 statements in this questionnaire, which included 13 questions about students' responses to the strategies used by English teachers in teaching reading, and 12 questions about the influence of strategies in reading a text, with responses ranging from very much Strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. Items in this questionnaire are verified based on the knowledge of the student played during the learning process.

Table 1. The strategy category used by the English teacher

No.	Statements	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Analyze Vocabulary	36%	64%	0%	0%
2.	Previewing	27%	55%	0%	18%
3.	Summarizing	14%	82%	0%	4%
4.	QARs	23%	50%	4%	23%

The most common strategy among the 25 statements is summarizing, at this ratio, most students choose the option strongly agree 14%, agree 82%, disagree 0% and strongly disagreed 4% stated that they agree with the statement because according to the student's perception, the strategy summarizing can help students in finding the process of identifying important information and ideas in a text. Previewing, students chose the option strongly agree 27%, agree 55%, strongly disagree 18% and no one chose the option disagreed. Students agree that using a previewing strategy is better when teaching a text analytical exposition because it can help students find the intrinsic information of a text. Meanwhile, analyzing vocabulary on this ratio students choose the option of strongly agree 36%, agree 64%, and none choose Disagree and strongly disagree. Thus students agree that the strategy to analyze vocabulary can help students improve their reading ability and be useful to understand the text. The last one is the QARs strategy, at this ratio students choose the option strongly agree 23%, agree 50%, disagree 4%, and strongly disagree 23%. Students thus agreed that QARs strategies can improve reading skills and improve their ability to understand reading content.

Table 2. Students' responses to the strategies used by English teachers

No.	Statements	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Teachers use strategies that can help students learn reading	41%	55%	0%	4%
2.	I feel that the strategies used by the teacher in teaching reading are clear so that I am helped in understanding the reading material presented	64%	36%	0%	0%
3.	The use of strategies used by teachers is effective in learning reading	82%	18%	0%	0%
4.	I feel helped by the strategies used by the teacher in reading and understanding the text	50%	50%	0%	0%

5.	The use of interesting strategies makes me pay more attention to the lesson or makes me focus more	77%	18%	0%	5%
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Based on the statements above, The findings indicated that the students in the tenth grade agreed with the statement. Their comments provide evidence for it. (1) most students agreed that in learning teachers use strategies that match the materials taught so that they can help students in the learning process, (2) most students strongly agreed that the strategies used by teachers are very clear, so they can understand the material of the text taught, (3) almost all the students stated strongly agree that the strategy used by the teachers is very effective in learning reading, (4) students felt that strategies employed by the teacher in learning to read can help in understanding a text, (5) the majority of students said strongly in agreement if the use of interesting strategies makes students more attentive and focused in learning.

Some students also disagree strongly with the statement given. Their reasons are as follows, the first students feel that teachers do not use strategies suitable for learning so students do not feel helped in improving their reading ability. And also teachers don't use attractive strategies so they're not enthusiastic about learning.

Interview

In this part, the researcher described the result of the interview about students' perception of teachers' strategies in teaching reading for the tenth graders at MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang. The interview was distributed on February 21, 2024. There were 15 questions in this interview guideline. Among the 15 questions, consisted of 2 questions about the teacher's strategy used in learning and students' difficulties in learning reading, especially in analytical exposition texts. The results of student answers are described in the form of descriptions. From the research. The description of students' answers is described in the following paragraphs.

Table 1. Students' responses to the strategies used in learning

No	Question	Students Responses
1.	Is the strategy used by the teacher in learning fun?	All the students stated that the strategy used by the teacher is very fun with the reason that the strategy used is interesting and interactive so that the learning time is not boring
2.	Is the teacher's strategy appropriate for the material being taught?	All the students stated that the strategy used by the teacher was very appropriate for the material being taught
3.	When your teacher uses certain strategies, what difficulties do you experience?	Some students expressed difficulty when the teacher used the summarizing strategy, arguing that the text was too long and they did not understand the meaning of the text. Other students also said that when using the question-and-answer strategy the teacher used English so they did not understand the meaning. It can be concluded that all students had difficulty in translating the text.

Table 2. Students' difficulties or problems in learning to read analytical exposition texts

No	Question	Students Responses
1.	Do you understand when the teacher explains English lessons, especially analytical exposition text?	Some students stated that they understood because before every lesson the teacher gave an understanding and explained in more detail what analytical text was. Other students stated that they did not understand because the teacher usually used English when explaining
2.	What are the things that make you find it difficult to understand analytical exposition text?	Most students stated that the text was too long which made it difficult for them to understand the analytical exposition text. Others stated that they did not have much vocabulary so it was difficult when read because they did not know the meaning
3.	Do you have trouble finding the sentences pro and contra in analytical exposition text?	14 students stated that they did not find it difficult to find the sentences pro and contra in a text. However, 8 students stated that it was very difficult because they did not understand the material and they did not know the meaning of analytical exposition text

4. Conclusion

In the research that has been conducted on "Students' Perception Towards Teacher Strategies In Teaching Reading For The Tenth Graders At MA Ma'arif Miftahul Ulum Melirang", the researcher concluded that based on the findings show that teachers usually use analyze vocabulary, previewing, summarizing and QARs strategies. From both the data taken using questionnaires and interviews, students have a positive perception of the strategies used by teachers in learning reading, especially in analytical exposition texts. The use of strategies increases their happiness and comfort levels in learning, increases their activity or excitement when learning English, prevents them from becoming bored, and makes it easier for them to comprehend the text, identify pro and contra sentences in analytical exposition text, and expand their vocabulary, and enhance their reading abilities. But, some students stated that teachers didn't use appropriate strategies so they weren't enthusiastic about learning. So it can be concluded that students' perceptions of the strategies used by teachers in teaching reading, especially analytical exposition texts, are positive.

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